

STUDENTS' VIEWS OF E-ASSESSMENT FEEDBACK IN UNDERGRADUATE MATHEMATICS

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This paper reports on undergraduate mathematics students' views on the feedback delivered through an e-assessment system, based on thematic analysis of interviews with 20 students. The results highlight students' views on the content of feedback – with many students expressing a preference for detailed, specific feedback, and mixed opinions about whether e-assessment delivered this. Students also reported strategic approaches to using the feedback. The findings resonate with existing frameworks on students' interactions with feedback, and provide a basis for further work to explore students' views toward e-assessment feedback in other contexts.

INTRODUCTION

Undergraduate mathematics education has increasingly embraced e-assessment as a tool for both formative and summative purposes (Kinnear, Jones, et al., 2022). Much previous research has investigated students' views about assessment, since these views influence how students approach their studies (Van der Kleij & Lipnevich, 2020). For instance, Iannone and Simpson (2015) found that mathematics students expressed a preference for more traditional forms of assessment, including closed-book exams, in contrast to findings in other disciplines. However, students' views about e-assessment have so far received relatively little attention.

Researchers studying the use of e-assessment within undergraduate mathematics have begun to explore students' views, and how these interact with students' activity. In Norway, Rønning (2017) surveyed engineering mathematics students and found that they appreciated getting feedback immediately on their weekly e-assessments – although they were not satisfied with the quality of the feedback, which gave “no indication of the reason for an error” (p. 96). This sometimes led to students adopting an approach of “hunting for the answer” (p. 101). In the US, Dorko (2020) combined observations of students working on e-assessment tasks with follow-up interviews, to develop a model of students' engagement. This study highlighted the cyclic nature of students' work on e-assessment tasks, particularly where multiple attempts were allowed, since students used initial attempts as “formative assessment to inform their work on the rest of a problem” (p. 463).

These studies highlight the importance of the way that students view feedback from e-assessment. While there is a large body of work on student perceptions of feedback (for a review, see Van der Kleij & Lipnevich, 2020), very little of this has focused on e-assessment feedback, and less still on undergraduate mathematics.

Our research question for this study was: what are students' views toward e-assessment feedback in an undergraduate mathematics course?

THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

Van der Kleij and Lipnevich (2020) reviewed 164 studies on students' perceptions of feedback. They summarised the findings about factors that influenced students' views under three broad headings: characteristics of the feedback, characteristics of the student, and the student response to the feedback. For our study, we did not seek to investigate whether characteristics of the students (e.g., gender, age, or other demographic variables) moderated their perceptions; the summary of previous research indicated studies of those characteristics tended to have findings that were inconclusive, or inconsistent across studies. The other two factors are relevant for our study, and were elaborated on by Lipnevich and Smith (2022) in their proposed model for the entire student-feedback interaction.

Regarding characteristics of the feedback, Lipnevich and Smith (2022) highlighted various aspects, including the timeliness, accuracy, and level of detail. All of these are pertinent to our study of views about e-assessment feedback, where these characteristics may be expected to differ from other forms of assessment (for instance, e-assessment feedback can be delivered more quickly than written feedback).

The student response to feedback is a crucial part of the model proposed by Lipnevich and Smith (2022). Their model emphasises students' generation of "self-feedback" in response to feedback messages, which can be described using three questions: "Do I understand the feedback? How do I feel about the feedback? What am I going to do with the feedback?" (p. 3). These three questions capture respectively the cognitive, affective and behavioural responses to feedback, which "interact with one another and result in self-feedback that defines action – or in a decision not to do anything about the feedback." (Lipnevich & Smith, 2022, p. 3).

Through their review, Van der Kleij and Lipnevich (2020) highlighted that interviews were a commonly-used method for research on this topic (64 out of 164 studies), although a majority of those had "serious methodological violations" (p. 358), which we sought to avoid in our study.

METHOD

We carried out semi-structured interviews with 20 students studying the same first-year pure mathematics course at a research-intensive UK university. The course is one third of a normal load for the semester, notionally requiring 200 hours of study across the 11-week semester. The course includes weekly written assignments that are marked by tutors (together counting for 25% of the course grade), and weekly e-assessment quizzes delivered through the STACK e-assessment system (for another 25% of the course grade). The e-assessment quizzes feature novel task types, including proof comprehension tasks (as described by Bickerton & Sangwin, 2021).

The interview questions aimed to elicit students' views about various aspects of e-assessment; one planned question that was particularly relevant to the analysis here was: "what do you think of the feedback that you get from STACK?". Participants were also prompted to make comparisons with the traditional written assessments in the course. All students on the course were invited to participate, and 20 students responded. We interviewed the students in March 2022, with 11 students in person (assigned pseudonyms beginning with P) and 9 online (assigned pseudonyms beginning with S). All interviews were recorded and later transcribed.

For the analysis, we used a thematic analysis approach (Braun & Clarke, 2006). We used descriptive coding in the first round of analysis, and developed themes and sub-themes from these. We revisited all transcripts to check that the themes were representative and identify relevant passages that had been missed in the first round.

RESULTS

The overall thematic map is shown in Table 1. For reasons of space, the analysis we report here is focused on the "Response to feedback" theme only.

Theme	Sub-themes
Approach to assessment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use of time • Work with others • Activity (reading, writing, watching lectures)
Response to feedback	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Content of the feedback • Using the feedback • Focus on marks • Timing of the feedback
Appreciation of the assessment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Emotions • Learning and study approaches • Developing mathematical skills

Table 1: Themes and sub-themes developed from the interviews.

Content of the feedback

Students consistently expressed a preference for feedback that is specific and detailed, and accordingly tended to favour the feedback that they got on written work over the e-assessment feedback. However, several students noted that detailed feedback on written work was not provided consistently. For instance, S1 said that "I don't think I've ever got particularly detailed feedback for the hand-ins", and that they found the e-assessment feedback helpful because "it'll usually give a solution". S8 also appreciated the worked solutions provided in the e-assessment feedback, since "you can see how it's meant to be done", in contrast with feedback on written work which is "just sorta saying where you went wrong and ... not much like, well, feedback on

what you need to change”. Many of the students also commented favourably on the depth of explanation in the e-assessment feedback. For instance, P11 described the feedback as “really helpful” and highlighted how in solutions to multiple-choice questions “it talks about each case ... tells you, oh yeah, this one’s right, this one’s wrong, here’s why it’s both of them ... it’s just really helpful with the detail”.

Many students expressed dissatisfaction with e-assessment feedback that was limited to a score and “just a kind of generic solution - here’s how to solve this question” (S1). Indeed, P6 characterised this as “not really feedback”. Many students compared this feedback to feedback they received on written work, which is “actually marked by people, so they can point out specific things” (P11). S7 explained that tutors can “pinpoint exactly where we went wrong and they can, like, suggest a better solution to it”, whereas the e-assessment feedback “can’t tell me how I went wrong”. In fact, the e-assessment system does have the facility to include specific comments based on the student answer, provided the teacher has programmed this in advance (for an example, see Alarfaj & Sangwin, 2022). P11 recalled receiving some feedback like this: “sometimes it will say, oh yeah, this wouldn’t work because of such and such ... I don’t know if it does that all the time, but sometimes it will, and it’s very helpful”. Similarly, P10 said that e-assessment feedback will “most of the time ... tell you where you’ve gone wrong”, although “there have definitely been sometimes where even after reading it, I’ve maybe been like, so where did I go wrong then?”.

Some students identified other drawbacks of the e-assessment feedback being largely limited to a score and a model answer. P7 noted that sometimes the model answer was “repeating something I guess I could read in the textbook” which was not helpful if that explanation “didn’t click”. S6 found that the model answers could help them see the correct answer but “it doesn’t necessarily help me from like an exam perspective ... because it doesn’t really tell me how exactly I should be writing down the solution”; they also described how their tutorial classes would often include discussion of the relative merits of different solution methods, and “that kind of feedback is missing” in the e-assessments.

Using the feedback

Several students emphasised the independence required to process and respond to the e-assessment feedback when it took the form of a model solution (which highlights the connection between this sub-theme and the “content of the feedback” sub-theme). For instance, P7 described how:

there are some questions where the feedback doesn’t help at all ... I’ve no idea why my version isn’t correct if I’ve done it in a slightly different way ... [the e-assessment feedback] will just tell me I’m wrong, and I will have to figure out why myself, or what I need to fix myself.

This independent sense-making is more difficult when the model solutions omit steps in the working: S1 noted that “it might take me a while to figure it out if I didn’t really understand how to do the question to begin with, then sometimes I’ll find there’s steps

they're skipping that I'm not totally sure about". Nevertheless, it seemed that many students persisted in their efforts: for instance, P8 described how "at first I throw my hands up and go, great, but then I probably just go over the notes again and try to understand, yeah, make sense of it in the context of the notes".

Other students described using the feedback for more general purposes, by extrapolating beyond the individual tasks that the feedback was addressing. P8 said they used the e-assessment feedback to identify topics they needed to revisit, and noted that getting things wrong "helps you then reflect more deeply on stuff you've learned". Similarly, P10 valued the e-assessments providing a means "to be able to actually know where we're at, to make progress, to ask questions, to know what we need to read more into, to just, like, develop our understanding".

Students also described making decisions about when to seek further help, from peers or their teachers, on the basis of the feedback. P10 said that when the e-assessment feedback presented a model solution based on a different method to the one they had used, they approached friends on the course who had used the same method to compare working and find the step where they had gone wrong. P11 said that after reviewing the feedback, "if you feel that you're not doing well, then you can bring it up with people, like, ask tutors about it". However, students were not always proactive in seeking help; for instance, P5 described finding the e-assessment feedback hard to understand, and said that "sometimes I ask the tutor in the tutorial, but other times, I just ignore".

Many students described using the e-assessment feedback in a strategic way. One strategy was specific to e-assessments where multiple attempts were allowed: some students described using an initial attempt as a means to see the worked solutions, which they could then use to guide their work on an actual attempt at the quiz. For instance, P6 described entering a "random answer, just so I can get that yellow box" with the worked solution. Similar behaviour has been identified in previous research on students' use of e-assessment (Kinnear, Wood, et al., 2022), where it was described as "gaming the system".

Another way that students were strategic was through engaging selectively with the feedback, including making choices about whether or not to act on it. For instance, P7 described reviewing the feedback to "look through all the ones I got wrong", but that they "don't normally go back immediately and fix the stuff ... my plan is to go back once I've finished my lectures and tutorials and use those quizzes for revision". P9 said that they would look at their score after the deadline for the assessed quiz, but would rarely seek out the feedback, because "it's a hassle to go back, it's more work ... with everything else going on". P11 shared an example of a recent e-assessment where they "didn't think the answer ... that was given, was actually right", and that they "checked it with someone else who's in second year and they actually agreed with me". When asked what they should do in that situation, they said they "don't really know", so this situation was ultimately unresolved.

Focus on marks

Related to the selective engagement with feedback described above, several students were particularly focused on the mark, rather than any other features of the feedback. P7 described checking the feedback when it is released, to “check what I got”, and “if it’s a much lower mark than I expected, I’ll scan down to see what sort of things”, while S5 said “if I’ve got over 80%, it’s generally nothing to worry about”.

One aspect of this focus on marks that caused particular tension with e-assessment was the students’ desire for partial credit. Students highlighted instances where they had made an error but had much of the working correct; for instance, P9 noted that “you could just misinterpret a question, have something that’s say double the number that they expect, and you get zero points, whereas on a hand-in, you might’ve gotten partial marks”. Another common issue is where the answer was expected in a particular form: S2 said entering answers in the right format had “been problematic a lot”, giving the example of “when integrating and adding a constant ... do you have to do a capital C or a lower case C? And people would just like completely get the question wrong cause they did a capital instead of lower case”. While several students were frustrated by losing marks over syntax errors, S5 was more relaxed: “I always tend to find that you’re not necessarily getting the understanding incorrect ... if I’ve got a question wrong because I’ve entered a number wrong, I won’t worry about it”.

Timing of the feedback

Many students commented on the timing of feedback from e-assessment, particularly in light of different settings used for two types of quizzes in this course: the formative “lecture quiz” gave immediate feedback while the summative “assessed quiz” only gave feedback after the deadline had passed. Most students expressed a preference for immediate feedback, while the question was still fresh in their mind, and noted that turnaround times on written assignments were typically much longer than for the e-assessments. S8 said that on the lecture quiz, “if I get the question wrong then I am thinking about the question, so I’m much more likely to look at the feedback”, while S9 said that for the assessed quiz:

by the time I get to review my answers, it’ll be a couple of days after I did it, and I’ve sort of lost, like, a track of why I wrote what I wrote, I just know that I got it wrong, so it doesn’t, like, help me learn as much.

For this reason, S1 completes STACK quizzes near the deadline, so “you can get the feedback the next day, which is nice”. While most students preferred immediate feedback, P7 said they disliked assessed quizzes in another course that gave feedback on each question as it was completed, because it “probably negatively affects my performance on later questions if I know I’ve already got a few ones beforehand wrong”.

DISCUSSION

We interviewed 20 undergraduate mathematics students about their views on e-assessment, and identified four sub-themes in their response to e-assessment feedback. First, regarding content of the feedback, detailed and personalised feedback was seen as desirable. Second, students described strategic approaches to using the feedback, in light of the effort required to independently process the feedback they received. Third, many students had a focus on marks rather than elaborated feedback, and were dissatisfied with the way that e-assessment often did not give partial credit. Fourth, students expressed a preference for immediate feedback.

Our interviews were designed to explore a range of issues related to e-assessment, not just the views about feedback that we have reported here. More focused interviews may have elicited more detail, and could have explicitly targeted issues that are highlighted in existing frameworks on feedback. On the other hand, our relatively open, semi-structured approach allowed for participants to raise the issues that mattered most to them. While our thematic analysis was inductive, the sub-themes that we identified have nevertheless aligned with aspects of existing frameworks; for instance, our “use of feedback” sub-theme is in line with the emphasis of Lipnevich and Smith (2022) on the way that students engage with feedback.

A limitation of our study is that it took place in one particular context, which will inevitably have shaped students’ views. For instance, at this institution, students are used to completing weekly e-assessment tasks that make up a small part of the course grade. In the interviews, students would sometimes compare e-assessment practices between courses (e.g., the course we targeted provided delayed feedback while another course provided immediate feedback during quiz attempts). Further study in other contexts would therefore be welcome, to gain insight into the role of context in shaping students’ views.

In future work, we plan to use our findings to develop and validate a survey, to examine students’ views on a larger scale. In their review of previous research on students’ perceptions of feedback, Van der Kleij and Lipnevich (2020) found that survey methods were widespread, although “the overall rigour of survey methodology in the selected studies was poor” (p. 365), so there is scope to make a worthwhile contribution by developing and validating the survey with a rigorous approach (cf. Muis et al., 2014).

References

- Alarfaj, M., & Sangwin, C. (2022). Updating STACK Potential Response Trees Based on Separated Concerns. *International Journal of Emerging Technologies in Learning (iJET)*, 17(23), Article 23. <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijet.v17i23.35929>
- Bickerton, R. T., & Sangwin, C. J. (2021). Practical online assessment of mathematical proof. *International Journal of Mathematical Education in Science and Technology*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0020739X.2021.1896813>

Braun, V., & Clarke, V. (2006). Using thematic analysis in psychology. *Qualitative Research in Psychology*, 3(2), 77–101. <https://doi.org/10.1191/1478088706qp063oa>

Dorko, A. (2020). Red X's and green checks: A model of how students engage with online homework. *International Journal of Research in Undergraduate Mathematics Education*, 6(3), 446–474. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40753-020-00113-w>

Iannone, P., & Simpson, A. (2015). Students' preferences in undergraduate mathematics assessment. *Studies in Higher Education*, 40(6), 1046–1067. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03075079.2013.858683>

Kinnear, G., Jones, I., Sangwin, C., Alarfaj, M., Davies, B., Fearn, S., Foster, C., Heck, A., Henderson, K., Hunt, T., Iannone, P., Kontorovich, I., Larson, N., Lowe, T., Meyer, J. C., O'Shea, A., Rowlett, P., Sikurajapathi, I., & Wong, T. (2022). A collaboratively-derived research agenda for E-assessment in undergraduate mathematics. *International Journal of Research in Undergraduate Mathematics Education*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40753-022-00189-6>

Kinnear, G., Wood, A. K., & Gratwick, R. (2022). Designing and evaluating an online course to support transition to university mathematics. *International Journal of Mathematical Education in Science and Technology*, 53(1), 11–34. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0020739X.2021.1962554>

Lipnevich, A. A., & Smith, J. K. (2022). Student – Feedback Interaction Model: Revised. *Studies in Educational Evaluation*, 75, 101208. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.stueduc.2022.101208>

Muis, K. R., Duffy, M. C., Trevors, G., Ranellucci, J., & Foy, M. (2014). What were they thinking? Using cognitive interviewing to examine the validity of self-reported epistemic beliefs. *International Education Research*, 2(1), 17–32.

Rønning, F. (2017). Influence of computer-aided assessment on ways of working with mathematics. *Teaching Mathematics and Its Applications: An International Journal of the IMA*, 36(2), 94–107. <https://doi.org/10.1093/teamat/hrx001>

Van der Kleij, F. M., & Lipnevich, A. A. (2020). Student perceptions of assessment feedback: A critical scoping review and call for research. *Educational Assessment, Evaluation and Accountability*, 33(2), 345–373. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11092-020-09331-x>